

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Project Title	The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns
Project Acronym	VeriFish
Project Number	101156426
Type of project	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01
Starting date of Project	01 May 2024
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.verifish.info

D3.8 VeriFish recipe book

Work Package	WPX WP Title
Task	T3.4 Media products & Stakeholder engagement campaigns
Lead author	Siân Astley (EUROFIR)
Contributors	Marion Buso (EUROFIR)
Peer reviewers	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)
Version	V1.0
Due Date	31/01/2026
Submission Date	30/01/2026

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public, fully open
	SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
	Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	27/01/2026	Marion Buso, Siân Astley (EUROFIR)	First version of the VeriFish recipe book, including an initial list of 19 recipes
1.0	30/01/2026	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Document review, formatting and upload

Keywords

VeriFish; VeriFish media products; aquafood sustainability; seafood sustainability; seafood, communication, seafood types, seafood consumers, communication strategies, fisheries, fishery, capture seafood; aquaculture, farmed seafood; seafood recipe book.

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafoods repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors like NOFIMA, EUROFIR and Poseidon. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document represents the initial, written version of the VeriFish Children’s “Let’s cook seafood” Recipe Book, designed to cater to children's taste preferences. At the current status the cookbook contains 19 recipes that will be available as a digital item via the VeriFish website at the URL <https://verifish.info/verifish-cookbook/>. Each of the recipes contains ingredients, cooking steps, alternatives for seafood type, fun facts about the species and nutritional information about the seafood species.

The content included in this deliverable will evolve in its digital version until the end of the VeriFish project, with new recipes to be added (up to 60) and made available via the VeriFish website, the VeriFish web-app, where they will be linked to the related factsheet species, and used as a reference also in other VeriFish dissemination materials such as the VeriFish Calendar.

The VeriFish Recipe book is a concrete example of implementation of the VeriFish indicator framework in a daily life context targeting families and European citizens at large. It focuses specifically on nutritional aspects, providing evidence of nutrition information per each recipe, combined with good sustainability profiles of the selected species based on the VeriFish environmental and socio-economic indicators.

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1. Introduction to the book

Welcome to the VeriFish Children’s “Let’s cook seafood” Recipe Book. This book is a fun and delicious way to explore seafood, healthy eating, and caring for our oceans! It includes a list of 60 recipes using different fish and seafood.

VeriFish is a European project supported by the Horizon Europe programme. Its goal is to help people better understand where seafood comes from, how it is produced, and how it can be enjoyed in a way that is good for our health and the planet. The project brings together trusted scientific information about seafood, including nutrition, environmental impact, and responsible production, to help everyone make more informed choices.

Seafood can sometimes be confusing: there are many species, different ways of producing them, and lots of information that is not always easy to understand. That’s why VeriFish creates simple and engaging tools, such as a website, a web-app, educational materials, and this recipe book, to make learning about seafood easier and more enjoyable.

This cookbook was created together with nutritionists and food experts to help children and adults cook simple, nutritious seafood dishes at home. The recipes are designed to match children’s taste preferences and to be easy and fun to prepare with adult supervision. Cooking together is a great way to learn new skills, try new foods, and build healthy eating habits from an early age.

The seafood species included in this book were carefully chosen. They are commonly eaten in Europe, suitable for family meals, and known for their valuable nutrients. Whenever possible, species with good sustainability profiles were selected, helping children and families discover seafood that supports both healthy diets and healthy oceans.

As you turn the pages, you will also find fun facts and nutritional information to help you learn more about the seafood you are cooking. A glossary of nutrition terms is included to explain what these nutrients do and how they benefit your health.

Before you start cooking, please read the instructions.

Have fun cooking!

1.1. Glossary Nutrition terms

Term	Definition
Nutrient	An element or compound needed for normal growth, development and health maintenance. Essential nutrients cannot be made by the body and must, therefore, be consumed from food
Dietary reference values (DRVs)	Amount of a nutrient needed to maintain health in an otherwise healthy individual or group of people.

Term	Definition
Macronutrient	A calorie-containing component of food (e.g. fat, protein, carbohydrate) which is needed in significant quantities for normal growth, development and maintenance of health
Carbohydrate	A type of macronutrient that includes sugars, starches and fibres and provides energy for the body.
Fibre	A type of carbohydrate that the body cannot fully digest. Fibers travel down to our digestive system and support your bowel movement and overall health
Sugars	Carbohydrate that provides quick energy for your body. It includes free sugars naturally present in honey, syrup, fruits and vegetables, and added sugars. It is better to moderate the amount of added sugar as too much of it can increase the risk of diseases
Protein	A type of molecule composed of complex strings of amino acids (protein building blocks). They are essential for building muscles, repairing tissues, making hormones and providing structure.
Fat	Fats are types of macronutrients that help the body store energy and produce hormones, support the brain and cells.
Saturated fat	A type of fat that increases blood cholesterol levels and the risk of heart disease. It is recommended to replace saturated fats in the diet with polyunsaturated fats like omega 3.
Omega 3	Omega 3 are polyunsaturated fat. Though they are necessary for our health, we cannot produce them ourselves. It supports brain, eye, and heart health and is found in foods like fish, nuts, and seeds.
Micronutrient	Dietary substance needed in very small amounts to support normal growth and maintenance of health in humans and animals. Most vitamins are 'essential' as they are not made within the body
Minerals	A naturally occurring inorganic element (e.g. calcium, iron) that is needed in the diet for normal growth, development and health
Iodine	Iodine is an essential mineral primarily involved in the synthesis of thyroid hormones. It also plays a critical role in the development of the foetal brain and nervous system.
Selenium	An essential mineral that acts as an antioxidant in the body and is involved in the good functioning of the thyroid and the immune system.
Zinc	Zinc is an essential mineral with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. It plays a crucial role in cellular functions and normal growth and development during pregnancy.
Iron	Iron is an essential mineral involve in the formation of red blood cells and the transport of oxygen in the body, and immune functions.
Calcium	Calcium is an essential mineral needed for healthy bones and teeth, for nerves and enzymes to function properly, and for blood clotting.

Term	Definition
Sodium	Sodium is a mineral that is part of salt (sodium chloride) and is essential for metabolic processes. High sodium intakes are linked to high blood pressure and other health issues.
Vitamin	Dietary substance needed in very small amounts to support normal growth and maintenance of health in humans and animals. Most vitamins are 'essential' as they are not made within the body
Vitamin D	Vitamin D is required to maintain normal blood levels of calcium and phosphate, important for the normal mineralisation of bone, muscle contraction, nerve conduction, and general cellular function.
Vitamin B12	Vitamin B12 is a water-soluble micronutrient found primarily in animal-derived foods that is essential for metabolic functions, red blood cell production, and nerve cell growth.
Vitamin B6	A group of vitamins needed for the protein metabolism, nervous and immune systems. It is also involved in the red blood cell formation.
Niacin	Niacin or vitamin B3 plays a crucial role in energy production and cellular functions.
Vitamin A	An essential nutrient needed in small amounts for the normal functioning of the visual system, growth and development, and maintenance of a healthy skin, immunity, and reproduction.

Table 1 – Glossary nutrition terms

1.2. About the nutrition information in the recipes

The nutrient values presented represent a selected group of key nutrients that are important for your health, including nutrients that may be under-consumed in some population groups, and that are commonly found in fish and seafood. These values aim to give an overall view of the nutritional benefits of each recipe but does not reflect the full nutrient profile of the recipes, as additional essential vitamins and minerals may also be present.

Nutritional values given in each recipe are expressed per serving and as a percentage of daily reference values based on EFSA dietary reference values for children aged 7–10 years. Nutrition values are presented per serving, together with the percentage of the daily reference value. The nutrition calculations are estimations, based on generic food products and average data available in European food composition tables.

1.3. INSTRUCTIONS (BEFORE YOU START COOKING)

Cooking is fun, creative, and super tasty but the kitchen is also a place where we need to be careful. Before you jump into your recipes, read these safety rules together with an adult.

 Beware of hot things

- Always use oven mitts when something might be hot.
- Never touch a pan, pot, baking tray, or oven door on your own.

 Be careful with sharp tools

- Knives, graters, and peelers are very helpful but only when used safely.
- Ask an adult to show you the safe way to hold and use them.

 Keep it clean

- Wash your hands before you start and after touching raw fish, meat, or eggs.
- Keep your workspace tidy so nothing slips, spills, or gets mixed by accident.

 Read the recipe first

- Look through the whole recipe before you begin.
- This helps you know what ingredients you need and where an adult might be needed.

 Have fun!

Cooking is teamwork. Talk, taste, try new things, and enjoy making delicious food together!

2. VeriFish Recipes

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Cod nuggets

6 servings

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: 20 min

Ingredients

- 650g Fresh cod
- 30g All-purpose flour
- Two large eggs
- 1 tsp oregano
- Half a tsp lemon zest
- 75g bread crumbs
- oil (for brushing)
- salt & pepper

For serving: ketchup, tartare sauce or lemon wedges

Steps (👨🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Pre-heat your oven to 220°C. Place a sheet a parchment paper on a big baking tray.
 2. Cut the cod into small pieces, about the size of a walnut. 👨🍳⚠️
 3. Put the cod pieces in a large bowl and sprinkle the flour over them. Mix gently until all the pieces are lightly coated.
 4. In a In a shallow bowl, whisk the eggs with the lemon zest, salt, pepper seasoning and put the breadcrumbs in another shallow bowl.
 5. Coat the fish: Dip the floured cod pieces into the egg mixture. Let the extra egg drip off. Roll them in the breadcrumbs until they're covered and crunchy.
 6. Place the coated cod pieces on the baking tray. Brush them with a little oil
 7. Bake for 20–25 minutes, until the nuggets are crispy and golden. 👨🍳⚠️
- Add a tiny pinch of salt if you like, and serve with ketchup, tartar sauce, or lemon wedges.

Alternative: Instead of cod, you can also use another white fish such as haddock or Alaska pollock, or even an oily fish like salmon. Please note that changing the type of fish will also change the nutritional values shown for this recipe.

Fun facts: Cod fish has been a popular fish to trade since the Viking times!

Female cod can lay million of eggs per season and some cod fish can reach up to 2 meters long and weigh up to 90 kg!

Cod is also very healthy and provides plenty of proteins, vitamins like niacin and vitamin B12 and minerals, such as iodine and selenium!

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal)					
Energy	220 kcal (12% DRV*)	Fat	4.4 g (7% DRV)	Iodine	283 ug (315% DRV)
Carbs	15.8 g (7% DRV)	Saturated fats	1.1 g (6% DRV)	Zinc	0.9 mg (7% DRV)
Fiber	1.2 g (7% DRV)	Omega 3	0.3 g (132% DRV)	Vit A	35 ug (9% DRV)
Sugar	0.9 g (2% DRV)	Sodium	469 mg (28% DRV)	Vit D	0.2 ug (2% DRV)
Protein	28.7 g (103% DRV)	Calcium	44 mg (6% DRV)	Niacin	2.8mg (24% DRV)
		Selenium	35 ug (101% DRV)	Vit B6	0.2 mg (20% DRV)
		Iron	1.2 mg (11% DRV)	Vit B12	2.1 ug (84% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
 These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://recipecenter.giantfood.com/recipes/169337/crispy-cod-nuggets>

Haddock fish pie

6-8 servings

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: 20 min

Ingredients

- 350g fresh haddock, skinned
- 350g smoked haddock, skinned
- 75g butter
- 1 large onion, roughly chopped
- 50g plain flour
- 570ml milk
- Salt & pepper (half a tsp each)
- 2 tbsp lemon juice
- 4 eggs
- 900g potatoes
- 50g butter (for the potatoes)
- 120ml milk (for the potatoes)

Steps (👨🍳⚠️ : adult needed step)

1. Get ready: grease a large baking dish with a little butter and pre-heat the oven to 200°C
2. Set your ingredient: Boil the eggs for 10 min. Chop the onion into small cubes, cut the fresh and smoked fish into small pieces (the size of a blueberry). Once the eggs are boiled and cooled down, remove the shells and roughly chop them (👨🍳⚠️ ask an adult to help!).
3. Melt a little butter in the pan and add the chopped onion. Cook for 15min with a lid on at medium heat. 👨🍳⚠️
4. Add the flour and stir. Gradually pour in the milk and keep stirring. 👨🍳⚠️
5. Add the chopped fresh fish, salt, pepper, lemon juice. Stir and cook for a few minutes until the fish is just cooked (about 5 min). 👨🍳⚠️
6. Add the smoked chopped fish and stir. Remove from the heat and pour the fish mixture into the baking dish (👨🍳⚠️). Add the chopped boiled eggs on top.
7. Prepare the mashed potatoes: peel the potatoes, cut them into small cubes and boil them for about 15 min (you should be able to insert a fork in easily). Drain well and add the milk and butter and mash until smooth. Add a little salt and pepper. 👨🍳⚠️

8. Add the mashed potatoes on top of the fish mixture in the baking tray and use a fork to make little lines on top.
9. Bake in the oven for about 30 minutes.

Fun facts: Haddock is the classic fish for the famous British fish and chips. It is low in fat, rich in protein, and provides essential vitamins, like B12 and B6 which are important for your blood, nerves and overall energy. Haddock are very easy to spot as they have a distinct dark lateral line running along their sides.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal))					
Energy	600 kcal (33% DRV*)	Fat	25.4 g (42% DRV)	Iodine	327 ug (363% DRV)
Carbs	47.7 g (21% DRV)	Saturated fats	15.3 g (77% DRV)	Zinc	2.4 mg (18% DRV)
Fiber	4.5 g (28% DRV)	Omega 3	0.3 g (111% DRV)	Vit A	279 ug (70% DRV)
Sugar	10.5 g (23% DRV)	Sodium	1002 mg (59% DRV)	Vit D	1.4 ug (10% DRV)
Protein	42.6 g (125% DRV)	Calcium	267 mg (33% DRV)	Niacin	6.5 mg (54% DRV)
		Selenium	57 ug (162% DRV)	Vit B6	0.7 mg (72% DRV)
		Iron	3 mg (27% DRV)	Vit B12	2.6 ug (106% DRV)
* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)					
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables					

Adapted from: https://www.bbc.co.uk/food/recipes/mary_berrys_fish_pie_79943

Hake in tomato sauce

6 servings

Prep time: 15 min

Cooking time: 15 min

Ingredients

- 6 medium fillets skinless and boneless hake fillets
- 2 tbsp fresh parsley leaves
- 2 tbsp of olive oil
- 2 garlic cloves
- 400g of tinned tomatoes
- 1 tsp sugar
- Half a tsp lemon zest
- 1 tsp turmeric
- 1 tsp chilli flakes
- 100ml water
- Salt & pepper

Steps (👨‍🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. In a large pan add all the ingredient for the sauce in a pan and cook until it simmers (when you see small bubbles). 👨‍🍳⚠️
2. Add the hake fillets, cover and cook for 15 minutes. 👨‍🍳⚠️
3. Serve on top of mashed potatoes, top with fresh parsley and enjoy!

Fun fact: Hake are fish that like to swim in groups! They usually stay very deep but come up at night. They are also a popular lean fish: they are a good source of protein but also essential minerals like iodine, helping your growth and energy, and selenium, important for the immune system!

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal))					
Energy	259 kcal (14% DRV*)	Fat	8.7 g (15% DRV)	Iodine	101.3 ug (113% DRV)
Carbs	4.2 g (2% DRV)	Saturated fats	1.4 g (7% DRV)	Zinc	1.6 mg (12% DRV)
Fiber	0.8 g (5% DRV)	Omega 3	0.6 g (254% DRV)	Vit A	30.5 ug (8% DRV)
Sugar	3.5 g (8% DRV)	Sodium	512 mg (30% DRV)	Vit D	4.3 ug (29% DRV)
Protein	40.4 g (144% DRV)	Calcium	68.3 mg (9% DRV)	Niacin	3.9 mg (33% DRV)
		Selenium	70.1 ug (200% DRV)	Vit B6	0.3 mg (33% DRV)
		Iron	2.8 mg (25% DRV)	Vit B12	2 ug (81% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
 These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://www.bordbia.ie/recipes/fish-recipes/poached-hake-with-a-simple-tomato-sauce/>

Plaice tacos

12 tacos

Prep time: 15min

Cooking time: 4min

Ingredients

- Plaice fillet (4 medium fillets) or other white fish
- 1/2 small lettuce
- 1 avocado
- 4 spring onions
- Coriander (or parsley) for topping
- Salt & pepper
- 12 taco-sized corn or flour totillas (35-30g each)

For the sauce

- 120g of Greek yogurt
- 1 tbsp lime juice
- 2 tbsp mild sriracha sauce (optional)
- 60g mayonnaise
- A pinch of salt

Steps (👩🍳⚠️ : adult needed step)

1. Prepare the sauce (add all ingredient together and mix) and set aside
2. Cut the veggies: spring onion, avocado and lettuce. 👩🍳
2. Add salt and pepper on the raw fish
3. Add the cooking oil in a pan and fry the fish when the pan is hot and cook for 4 min (2 min on each side) or until opaque (very white). 👩🍳⚠️
4. Spread all the ingredient in one taco or small tortilla and add one or two tablespoon of sauce and some coriander (or parsley)

Bon Appetit!

Note: you can also use red cabbage instead of lettuce

Fun facts: Plaice is a flatfish that can live up to 50 years! It's low in fat, high in protein, and a good source of D and B-vitamins: perfect for growing muscles and a healthy brain!

Nutrition (per serving – 1 taco of the the composite meal))					
Energy	225 kcal (13%DRV*)	Fat	11.6 g (19%DRV)	Iodine	25.4 ug (28%DRV)
Carbs	17.1 g (8%DRV)	Saturated fats	2.2 g (11%DRV)	Zinc	0.6 mg (5%DRV)
Fiber	1.7 g (11%DRV)	Omega 3	0.1 g (40%DRV)	Vit A	36.3 ug (9%DRV)
Sugar	1.8 g (4%DRV)	Sodium	419 mg (25%DRV)	Vit D	0.5 ug (4%DRV)
Protein	12.4 g (44%DRV)	Calcium	41.4 mg (5%DRV)	Niacin	1.8 mg (15%DRV)
		Selenium	20.9 ug (60%DRV)	Vit B6	0.2 mg (19%DRV)
		Iron	0.5 mg (5%DRV)	Vit B12	0.6 ug (25%DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
 These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: https://www.simplyrecipes.com/recipes/fish_tacos/

Pollock pitas

6 servings (6 pitas)

Prep time: 15 min

Cooking time: 8 min

Ingredients

- 6 frozen breaded Alaskan pollock fillets
- 6 pita breads
- 300g of Greek yogurt
- 1 tsp of lemon zest
- 1 tbsp of lemon juice
- ½ small lettuce, shredded
- 180g chopped tomatoes
- 180g chopped cucumbers
- Half a red onion

Steps (👩🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Cut the veggies into slices. 👩🍳⚠️
2. Cook the breaded pollock fillets: Heat a tablespoon of vegetable oil in a pan. place the frozen fillet in the pan and fry for 8 minutes over medium heat. Turn regularly. Pat with paper towels before serving. 👩🍳⚠️
3. Heat the pita breads in the oven or a toaster for a few minutes. 👩🍳⚠️
4. Mix the yogurt with the lemon juice and lemon zest
5. Assemble all the ingredients into your pita bread and add a tablespoon (or more) of yogurt sauce.

Fun facts: Pollock is a white fish related to cod. They have a mild taste which is perfect, and often used, for fish sticks! Pollock is also rich in protein, vitamin B12, as well as iodine and selenium. These are important for your muscles, growth, energy, and immune system.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal))					
Energy	461 kcal (26% DRV*)	Fat	16.1 g (27% DRV)	Iodine	100.2 ug (111% DRV)
Carbs	53.3 g (24% DRV)	Saturated fats	5.6 g (28% DRV)	Zinc	1.3 mg (10% DRV)
Fiber	3.6 g (23% DRV)	Omega 3	0.1 g (52% DRV)	Vit A	113.9 ug (28% DRV)
Sugar	6.9 g (15% DRV)	Sodium	681.1 mg (40% DRV)	Vit D	0 ug (0% DRV)
Protein	23.5 g (84% DRV)	Calcium	109.6 mg (14% DRV)	Niacin	3 mg (25% DRV)
		Selenium	24.7 ug (71% DRV)	Vit B6	0.1 mg (15% DRV)
		Iron	2 mg (18% DRV)	Vit B12	1.8 ug (73% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)

These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://www.simplotfoods.com/au/recipe/greek-style-fish-pita-pockets>

Whiting omelette

2 servings

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: 15 min

Ingredients

- 2 small whiting fillet (or other white fish)
- 4 large eggs
- Hand full of spinach
- 60g Mozzarella (shredded) (half a ball)
- 1 tbsp butter
- A squeeze of lemon
- Salt & pepper
- Parsley for topping (optional)

Steps (👩🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Cook the fish 👩🍳⚠️: with an adult, heat a pan, add the butter and place the fish in the pan. Cook a few minutes until it turns white and flaky. Put aside and break it into small pieces with a fork.
2. Set the fish aside and add the spinach to the same pan. Stir until it becomes soft and small. Turn off the heat and set aside. 👩🍳⚠️
3. Mix the eggs: crack the eggs into a bowl. Add a pinch of salt and pepper
4. Cook the omelette: with an adult, heat the pan again with some butter, pour in the eggs, when the eggs start setting (about 5 min), add the cooked fish, spinach and mozzarella. 👩🍳⚠️
5. Fold: use a spatula to fold the omelette in half and wait 1 min so the cheese melt. Serve and squeeze a bit of lemon on top if you'd like. 👩🍳⚠️

Enjoy this fishy omelette!

Fun facts: Fun fact: Whiting is a white fish like haddock or cod. It is a social fish, who likes to travel in large groups for safety.

It is rich in protein, low in fat and provides important nutrients like vitamin B12, selenium and iodine.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal))					
Energy	387 kcal (21%DRV*)	Fat	23.8 g (40%DRV)	Iodine	149.5 ug (166%DRV)
Carbs	2.2 g (1%DRV)	Saturated fats	11.7 g (59%DRV)	Zinc	3.9 mg (30%DRV)
Fiber	1.9 g (12%DRV)	Omega 3	0.2 g (89%DRV)	Vit A	490.9 ug (123%DRV)

Sugar	0.6 g (1%DRV)	Sodium	777.4 mg (46%DRV)	Vit D	4.6 ug (31%DRV)
Protein	39.8 g (142%DRV)	Calcium	221.4 mg (28%DRV)	Niacin	2.8 mg (23%DRV)
		Selenium	48.2 ug (138%DRV)	Vit B6	0.3 mg (35%DRV)
		Iron	5 mg (46%DRV)	Vit B12	3.3 ug (130%DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)

These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Seabream papillote

2 servings

Prep time: 5 min

Cooking time: 25 min

Ingredients

- Two seabream fillets
- 150g cherry tomatoes
- 50g Pitted black olives
- ½ tsp of dried herbes de provence mix
- 1 tbsp of lemon juice
- ½ tsp of garlic powder
- 1 tbsp olive oil
- Pinch of salt and pepper

Steps (👨🍳⚠️ : adult needed step)

1. Preheat your oven at 180°C and ask an adult to halve the cherry tomatoes and the black olives. 👨🍳⚠️
2. On an oven tray, place one large sheet of parchment paper over one of foil.
3. Put the fillets on the parchment paper with the rest of the dried ingredients.
4. Drizzle over the olive oil and the juice of one lemon. Now, seal the fillets by folding the spare parchment paper.
5. Bake them in the oven for 15 min. Once ready, carefully take them out and with care open the parchment paper for the steam to free. 👨🍳⚠️

Enjoy!

Fun facts: Some species of sea bream are hermaphrodites, this means they are born male and later become female. You can usually get them from half a kilo, but seabream can grow up until 3 kilos! Seabream is a healthy fish that offers valuable protein, omega-3s, and key nutrients such as vitamin D, vitamin B12, and selenium.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal))					
Energy	407 kcal (23%DRV*)	Fat	24.5 g (41% DRV)	Iodine	30.7 ug (34% DRV)
Carbs	5.8 g (3% DRV)	Saturated fats	4.3 g (21% DRV)	Zinc	1 mg (8% DRV)
Fiber	4.5 g (28% DRV)	Omega 3	1.5 g (611% DRV)	Vit A	63.6 ug (16% DRV)
Sugar	4.2 g (9% DRV)	Sodium	558.7 mg (33% DRV)	Vit D	4.8 ug (32% DRV)
Protein	38.3 g (137% DRV)	Calcium	63.6 mg (8% DRV)	Niacin	13.3 mg (111% DRV)
		Selenium	22.3 ug (64% DRV)	Vit B6	0.8 mg (77% DRV)

Iron	4.8 mg (43% DRV)	Vit B12	5 ug (199% DRV)
* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA) These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables			

Adapted from: <https://www.thefishsociety.co.uk/blogs/recipes/mediterranean-lemon-sea-bass-en-papillote>

Rainbow trout mac & cheese

6 servings

Prep time: 20 min

Cooking time: 10 min + 20 min in the oven

Ingredients

- 200g Rainbow fresh trout fillets (or unfrozen)
- 250g Macaroni pasta
- 40g Butter
- 5g Vegetable oil
- 40g All purpose flour
- 600 Milk
- 200g Cheddar cheese shredded
- 100g Liquid cream
- ½ tsp Garlic powder
- Salt and pepper

Steps (👨‍🍳⚠️ : adult needed step)

1. Cook the trout (if using fresh fillet or unfrozen): Cut the fillets in small pieces, add salt, pepper and garlic powder and cook 3-4 minutes in a hot pan with a bit of cooking oil. Set aside. 👨‍🍳⚠️
 2. Cook the macaroni following the package instructions. 👨‍🍳⚠️
 3. Prepare the cheesy bechamel: In a medium pot, melt the butter, add the flour and mix. Slowly add the milk and cream while still stirring to avoid any lump. Leave it to thicken at low heat. Once thick, add half of the shredded cheddar cheese and mix. 👨‍🍳⚠️
 4. In an oven dish: add the macaroni, pasta and sauce together and mix. Top with the other half of the shredded cheddar
 5. Bake in the oven for 20 min at 180°C. 👨‍🍳⚠️
- Enjoy this delicious creamy and comforting dish!

Fun facts: Rainbow trout are from the same family as salmon called Salmonidae.

They are very rich in protein, omega 3 and vitamin D, and also provide high levels of B-vitamins and minerals like selenium.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal)					
Energy	530 kcal (29%DRV*)	Fat	27.8 g (46% DRV)	Iodine	49 ug (54% DRV)
Carbs	42.3 g (19% DRV)	Saturated fats	16.4 g (82% DRV)	Zinc	2.2 mg (17% DRV)
Fiber	1.9 g (12% DRV)	Omega 3	0.3 g (119% DRV)	Vit A	211.9 ug (53% DRV)

Sugar	6.9 g (15% DRV)	Sodium	536.9 mg (32% DRV)	Vit D	4.2 ug (28% DRV)
Protein	26.5 g (95% DRV)	Calcium	457.5 mg (57% DRV)	Niacin	2.6 mg (22% DRV)
		Selenium	8.1 ug (23% DRV)	Vit B6	0.2 mg (19% DRV)
		Iron	1 mg (9% DRV)	Vit B12	2.1 ug (84% DRV)
* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)					
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables					

Tuna dip

6 servings

Prep time: 5 min

Cooking time: No cooking

Ingredients

- 1 pack cream cheese (e.g. Philadelphia)
- 1 tuna tin in water, drained
- 2 tbsp lemon juice
- Pepper & salt to taste
- Chives (to top)

Steps

This recipe is very quick:

1. Mix all the ingredient together in a medium bowl until it's smooth: tuna, cream cheese, lemon juice, salt and pepper

2. Top with chives

It's ready!

You can eat it on toast, or dip in chopped cucumbers and carrots

Fun facts: Tuna is a sleek fish that can grow very large: some species weigh over 600 kg! They are also very fast swimmers (some can go up to 75km an hour).

Tuna is very nutritious and rich in protein, omega-3, vitamin D and B-vitamins and minerals like selenium. Most canned tuna comes from leaner tuna species like the yellowfin or skipjack tuna.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal)					
Energy	162 kcal (9%DRV*)	Fat	12.2 g (20%DRV)	Iodine	6.8 ug (8%DRV)
Carbs	1.4 g (1%DRV)	Saturated fats	6.8 g (34%DRV)	Zinc	1.3 mg (10%DRV)
Fiber	0.1 g (1%DRV)	Omega 3	0.1 g (37%DRV)	Vit A	124.7 ug (31%DRV)
Sugar	0.9 g (2%DRV)	Sodium	247 mg (15%DRV)	Vit D	0.5 ug (4%DRV)
Protein	11.6 g (41%DRV)	Calcium	39.7 mg (5%DRV)	Niacin	4 mg (33%DRV)
		Selenium	27.7 ug (79%DRV)	Vit B6	0.1 mg (14%DRV)
		Iron	0.9 mg (8%DRV)	Vit B12	1.3 ug (54%DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)

These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Anchovy pizza

Serving: 1 pizza

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: 15 min

Ingredients

- 1 pizza dough
- 175g tomato paste
- 100g mozzarella cheese
- 4 to 6 anchovy fish fillet in oil and drained
- 2 tsp of dried oregano
- olive oil (to top)

Steps (👨🍳⚠️ : adult needed step)

1. Pre-heat your oven at 250°C

1. Roll the dough into a ring. Cover the dough with the tomato sauce in circular motion and sprinkle the dried oregano

2. chop the mozzarella roughly (you can shred it with your hands) and add the pieces and the anchovy fillets on the pizza

3. Bake the pizza for 12 to 15 minutes. 👨🍳⚠️

4. Take the pizza out of the oven, add a drizzle of olive oil and serve it. 👨🍳⚠️

Fun facts: Despite being tiny, anchovies are full of flavour and an excellent source of omega 3, vitamin D, selenium, iodine and a good source of iron.

In the sea, they travel in huge amount, sometimes millions together, to protect themselves from predators.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal – 2 slices)					
Energy	392 kcal (22% DRV*)	Fat	18.2 g (30%DRV)	Iodine	12.5 ug (14%DRV)
Carbs	41.1 g (18% DRV)	Saturated fats	5.6 g (28%DRV)	Zinc	1.4 mg (10%DRV)
Fiber	2.8 g (18% DRV)	Omega 3	0.1 g (26%DRV)	Vit A	102.7 ug (26%DRV)
Sugar	3.6 g (8% DRV)	Sodium	970.4 mg (57%DRV)	Vit D	0.8 ug (6%DRV)
Protein	14.3 g (51% DRV)	Calcium	77.1 mg (10%DRV)	Niacin	2.4 mg (20%DRV)
		Selenium	4.7 ug (13%DRV)	Vit B6	0.2 mg (17%DRV)
		Iron	1.3 mg (11%DRV)	Vit B12	0.5 ug (21%DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
 These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://www.giallozafferano.com/recipes/roman-pizza.html>

Mackerel patties

4-5 servings (10 patties)

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: 10 min

Ingredients

- 350g canned mackerel in water, drained (~3 tins)
- 2 eggs
- 25g parmesan cheese
- 50g breadcrumbs
- 2 tbsp of mayonnaise
- 2 tbsp of mustard
- 2 tbsp of chives or schallion, chopped
- Vegetable oil for frying
- Salt & pepper

Steps (👨🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Drain the mackerel, remove bones and place them in a medium bowl. Flake with a fork.
2. Prepare the mixture: add all the ingredient expect the oil: cheese, breadcrumbs, mayonnaise and mustard, the chives, and mix well!
3. Now the fun part: with your hands, shape into patties.
4. With an adult pour the oil into a pan and turn to heat. Fry the patties until golden brown (about 3 min each side). 🍳⚠️
5. Serves and enjoy! You can eat them with a any sauce you like: for example mayonnaise, sauce tartare or with a bit of squeezed lemon on top.

Fun facts: Mackerel are shiny, striped fish that can swim up to 50 km/h. They're an excellent source of protein, vitamin B12, vitamin D, and omega-3, which are good for your heart and brain.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal – 2 patties)					
Energy	359 kcal (20% DRV*)	Fat	26.9 g (45% DRV)	Iodine	54.9 ug (61% DRV)
Carbs	8.5 g (4% DRV)	Saturated fats	6.3 g (32% DRV)	Zinc	2.7 mg (21% DRV)
Fiber	0.8 g (5% DRV)	Omega 3	2.4 g (965% DRV)	Vit A	74.5 ug (19% DRV)
Sugar	1 g (2% DRV)	Sodium	682 mg (40% DRV)	Vit D	2.8 ug (19% DRV)
Protein	20.4 g (73% DRV)	Calcium	92.1 mg (12% DRV)	Niacin	3.8 mg (31% DRV)
		Selenium	36.8 ug (105% DRV)	Vit B6	0.1 mg (11% DRV)
		Iron	2.2 mg (20% DRV)	Vit B12	5 ug (200% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://cooktoria.com/mackerel-patties/#recipe>

Salmon wellington

8 servings

Prep time: 25 min

Cooking time: 18 min

Ingredients

- 2 large rectangle sheet of puff pastry
- 450g fresh salmon fillet without skin
- 120g spinach
- 1 garlic clove
- 1 tsp lemon juice
- 2 tsp mild mustard
- 1 tsp honey
- 1 egg
- 1 tbsp olive oil
- half a tsp salt

Steps (👨🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Cook the veggies (👨🍳⚠️): Heat a pan and add 1 tbsp olive oil. Add the garlic and spinach and cook until soft. Add one tsp lemon and a pinch of salt and set aside.
2. Make the honey-mustard sauce: In a small bowl, mix the mustard and the honey.
3. Cut the salmon in 8 pieces (👨🍳⚠️)
4. Prepare the puff pastry: cut it into 8 rectangles, on each put a spoon of the spinach mix in the middle, add one piece of salmon and spread a bit of the honey-mustard sauce on the salmon and a pinch of salt.
5. Cut the second puff pastry into 8 rectangles and add each on top of each salmon piece.
6. Now cut it like a fish (ask an adult to help) and seal each side with a fork.
7. Cut diagonal lines (👨🍳⚠️): Use a small knife to score the top of the pastry by cutting very shallow diagonal lines. Then score diagonal lines the other way to make a crosshatch pattern (Don't cut all the way through!)
8. Beat the egg and brush the top with the mixture.
9. Place each fish on a baking parchment in a baking tray. Bake for 15-18 minutes, until golden brown

Let cool for a few minutes and serve warm.

Fun facts: Salmon are amazing travellers! They grow up in the sea but swim all the way back to the river where they were born to lay their eggs.

They're also healthy fish as they are rich in protein, vitamin D, and omega-3.

Nutrition (per serving of the the composite meal)			
Energy	465 kcal (26%DRV*)	Fat	28 g (47% DRV)
Carbs	32.5 g (14% DRV)	Saturated fats	13.8 g (69% DRV)
Fiber	2.4 g (15% DRV)	Omega 3	1 g (386% DRV)
Sugar	3.2 g (7% DRV)	Sodium	490 mg (29% DRV)
Protein	19.6 g (70% DRV)	Calcium	108.6 mg (14% DRV)
		Selenium	23.2 ug (66% DRV)
		Iron	2.1 mg (19% DRV)
		Iodine	22.7 ug (25% DRV)
		Zinc	1.2 mg (9% DRV)
		Vit A	184.6 ug (46% DRV)
		Vit D	6 ug (40% DRV)
		Niacin	5.2 mg (43% DRV)
		Vit B6	0.4 mg (38% DRV)
		Vit B12	2.4 ug (95% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
 These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://happykidskitchen.com/pastry-wrapped-salmon-and-veggies/>

Baked breaded Sardine

6 servings

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: 15 min

Ingredients

- 240g canned sardines in olive oil
- 2 Eggs
- 40g Flour
- 2 tbsp of parsley
- 50g breadcrumbs
- 1 tbsp olive oil
- A pinch of salt and pepper

Steps (👩🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Preheat your oven at 200°C before starting.
2. Carefully open the canned sardines and drain the oil with the help of a strainer, set them aside. 👩🍳⚠️
2. Prepare the egg wash by whisking eggs, parsley, salt and pepper.
3. Now coat your sardines: first in flour, then dip them into the egg wash and finally coat them in breadcrumbs.
4. Place each fillet on a baking tray, drizzle olive oil and bake them for 10 min at 200°C or until golden brown. 👩🍳⚠️
5. Once they are ready, pop them out of the oven, and plate them.

You can have them just like in Spain with squeezed lemon and some mayonnaise!

Fun facts: The name of sardine comes from the island of Sardinia where they were very abundant! Sardines are very nutrient dense, packed with protein, omega-3s, vitamin D, B vitamins like vitamin B12, and mineral like selenium or calcium if you eat them with the bones.

Nutrition (per serving)					
Energy	172 kcal (10%DRV*)	Fat	8.9 g (15% DRV)	Iodine	18.2 ug (20% DRV)
Carbs	11.3 g (5% DRV)	Saturated fats	1.9 g (9% DRV)	Zinc	1.1 mg (8% DRV)
Fiber	0.8 g (5% DRV)	Omega 3	0.9 g (367% DRV)	Vit A	11.1 ug (3% DRV)
Sugar	0.5 g (1% DRV)	Sodium	354.4 mg (21% DRV)	Vit D	1.1 ug (7% DRV)
Protein	11.1 g (40% DRV)	Calcium	215.8 mg (27% DRV)	Niacin	2.8 mg (24% DRV)
		Selenium	21.5 ug (61% DRV)	Vit B6	0.1 mg (8% DRV)
		Iron	1.4 mg (13% DRV)	Vit B12	5.7 ug (228% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://spainonafork.com/spanish-style-fried-sardines-using-canned-sardines-recipe/>

Crab cakes

Servings: 8 patties

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: 10 min

Ingredients

- 1 large egg, beaten
- 80g mayonnaise
- 2 tbsp mild mustard
- A splash of mild sriracha sauce (or other hot sauce) (optional)
- Salt & pepper
- 450 g cooked crabmeat
- 70g breadcrumbs
- 2 tbsp fresh parsley optional)
- A little oil for frying

Steps (👨🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Mix the wet ingredients: In a medium bowl mix together: egg + mayonnaise + mustard + tiny splash hot sauce + pinch of salt and pepper
2. Add the crab meat, breadcrumbs and parsley to the mixture and mix
3. Shape the patties: scoop a handful and press them into little patties (like mini burgers)
If it feels too wet, add a bit of breadcrumbs
4. Cook 🍳⚠️: Heat a little oil in a pan over medium heat, cook the patties for 3 to 4 minutes per side until golden.

Transfer to a plate and serve warm with lemon wedges and a mild dip (mayo, tartar sauce, etc.) 😊

Tip: You can also serve the crab cakes with a green salad on the side!

Fun facts: Crabs are special sea creatures: They have 10 limbs: eight walking legs and two strong claws! Their meat is low in fat and very rich in proteins, vitamin B12 and minerals like zinc and selenium.

Nutrition (per serving – 2 patties)					
Energy	358 kcal (20% DRV*)	Fat	21.4 g (36% DRV)	Iodine	88.8 ug (99% DRV)
Carbs	14.7 g (7% DRV)	Saturated fats	3.2 g (16% DRV)	Zinc	7.2 mg (56% DRV)
Fiber	1.2 g (7% DRV)	Omega 3	0.4 g (158% DRV)	Vit A	48.2 ug (12% DRV)
Sugar	2.1 g (5% DRV)	Sodium	1149 mg (68% DRV)	Vit D	0.2 ug (1% DRV)
Protein	26 g (93% DRV)	Calcium	160.9 mg (20% DRV)	Niacin	1.5 mg (13% DRV)
		Selenium	35 ug (100% DRV)	Vit B6	0.3 mg (31% DRV)

Iron	3.7 mg (34% DRV)	Vit B12	0.2 ug (7% DRV)
* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA) These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables			

Adapted from: <https://www.delish.com/cooking/recipe-ideas/a58704/best-crab-cakes-recipe/>

Stuffed mussels

6 servings

Prep time: 20 min

Cooking time: 20 min

Ingredients

- 1kg mussels with shells
- A sprig of parsley
- 40g Breadcrumbs
- 25g Parmesan cheese
- 2 cloves Garlic
- 3 tbsp Olive oil
- 2 tbsp Basil leaves (fresh) (or substitute it with 1 tsp of dried basil)

Steps (👩🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. On a sauce pan, put water to boil. Once ready, carefully add the parsley sprig and mussels. 👩🍳⚠️
2. Let the mussels steam 10 min, or until they open. In the meantime, preheat your oven at 200°C
3. As they open, take them out of the sauce pan and place them on a plate. Use tongs as they are really hot. 👩🍳⚠️
4. Let's make the stuffing. Ask an adult to chop the garlic and basil for you. Now, in a bowl place the breadcrumbs, the cheese, the olive oil and the chopped garlic and basil. 👩🍳⚠️
5. Combine them all, the mixture should look like wet sand. With your hands stuff each half side of the mussels with the stuffing.
6. Place the stuffed mussels on a baking tray, drizzle olive oil on top and bake them for 10 minutes or until the stuffing gets golden brown.

Fun facts: Mussels are natural water filters! They help sea streams and lakes to be cleaned and safe for marine life. Did you know people farm mussels? They stick to floating rafts near the shore, so farmers raise them until they reach maturity and a big size.

Mussels are a nutritious seafood, high in protein, low in fat, and very rich in minerals such as selenium, and iodine, as well as vitamin B12.

Nutrition (per serving)					
Energy	176 kcal (10%DRV*)	Fat	11.1 g (19% DRV)	Iodine	53.3 ug (59% DRV)
Carbs	8.8 g (4% DRV)	Saturated fats	2.5 g (13% DRV)	Zinc	1.2 mg (9% DRV)
Fiber	0.5 g (3% DRV)	Omega 3	0.3 g (106% DRV)	Vit A	66.3 ug (17% DRV)
Sugar	0.5 g (1% DRV)	Sodium	225.4 mg (13% DRV)	Vit D	0 ug (0% DRV)

Protein	10 g (36% DRV)	Calcium	77.8 mg (10% DRV)	Niacin	0.7 mg (6% DRV)
		Selenium	20.6 ug (59% DRV)	Vit B6	0.1 mg (5% DRV)
		Iron	1.6 mg (15% DRV)	Vit B12	7.1 ug (284% DRV)
* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)					
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables					

Adapted from: https://www.bbc.co.uk/food/recipes/_stuffed_mussels_01612

Mini seafood quiche

Servings: 12 mini-quiche

Prep time: 20 min

Cooking time: 20 min

Ingredients

- One pre-made quiche dough
- Butter (to grease tray)
- 3 Egg
- 20 cl crème fraiche
- 20 cl Milk
- 2 tbsp chives or parsley
- Grated gruyere cheese
- 12 medium scallops with or without roe (alternatively you can also use shrimps)
- Salt & pepper

Steps (👨‍🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Pre-heat the oven at 200°C and grease a 12-muffin tray.
2. Cut the scallops (or shrimp if you are using shrimps) in small pieces. You can also decide to use the scallops whole directly (Tip: for a better consistency, you can sear the scallops lightly on each side in a pan 👨‍🍳⚠️)
3. In a large bowl, whisk together the eggs, crème fraiche, milk, cheese, salt and pepper.
4. Cut the dough in small circle and place them in a greased muffin tray. 👨‍🍳⚠️
5. Add a few pieces of shrimps or one scallop in each cup
6. Pour the filling into each cup almost to the top
7. Bake the mini-quiche for 20 to 25 min. 👨‍🍳⚠️

Fun facts: Scallops live in all the world's oceans and they are the only bivalve mollusc that can swim! Scallops are also very healthy and a great source of protein, vitamin B12, and minerals like selenium, iodine, and zinc!

Nutrition (per serving – 2 mini quiches) <i>(calculated using scallops without roe)</i>					
Energy	401 kcal (22% DRV*)	Fat	24 g (40% DRV)	Iodine	107.2 ug (119% DRV)
Carbs	24.2 g (11% DRV)	Saturated fats	13 g (65% DRV)	Zinc	1.9 mg (15% DRV)
Fiber	1.1 g (7% DRV)	Omega 3	0.1 g (50% DRV)	Vit A	260.9 ug (65% DRV)
Sugar	3.9 g (9% DRV)	Sodium	583 mg (34% DRV)	Vit D	0.7 ug (5% DRV)
Protein	21.4 g (76% DRV)	Calcium	197.8 mg (25% DRV)	Niacin	1.3 mg (11% DRV)

Selenium	21.1 ug (60% DRV)	Vit B6	0.2 mg (15% DRV)
Iron	1.4 mg (12% DRV)	Vit B12	1.6 ug (66% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Grilled shrimp skewers

8 skewers

Prep time: 30 min

Cooking time: 4-6 min grill or 6-8 min oven

Ingredients

- 450g large shrimp fresh or unfrozen, peeled
- 2 bell peppers, cut into big chunks
- 1 medium zucchini, cut into thick slices (about 1.5 cm)
- 60ml olive oil
- Lemon juice (about 2 tbsp)
- ½ tsp garlic powder
- ½ tsp salt
- ½ tsp black pepper

Before you start place 8 wooden skewers in water for 30 minutes to avoid burning

Steps (👩🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Make the marinade: whisk together the olive oil, lemon juice, garlic powder, salt and pepper.
2. Add the shrimp and veggies to the marinade, mix and set aside for 15 minutes.
3. Build the skewers: alternate between shrimp and vegetables.
4. Cook 👩🍳⚠️: place the skewers on a preheated grill. Cook each skewer 2–3 minutes per side. Shrimp should turn pink and opaque. Alternatively you can cook the skewers in the oven on a baking sheet: pre-heat to 220°C and bake for 6-8 minutes.

Fun facts: Shrimps are found all over the whole, with over 2000 species of shrimps! In cooking, they are very popular and they are also rich in proteins, vitamins, such as B12, and minerals like selenium and iodine.

Nutrition (per serving – 2 skewers)					
Energy	219 kcal (12%DRV*)	Fat	4.8 g (8%DRV)	Iodine	203.4 ug (226%DRV)
Carbs	11.2 g (5%DRV)	Saturated fats	0.8 g (4%DRV)	Zinc	4.7 mg (36%DRV)
Fiber	2.7 g (17%DRV)	Omega 3	0.5 g (186%DRV)	Vit A	140.2 ug (35%DRV)
Sugar	5.6 g (13%DRV)	Sodium	624.2 mg (37%DRV)	Vit D	0.3 ug (2%DRV)
Protein	31.3 g (112%DRV)	Calcium	155.7 mg (19%DRV)	Niacin	5.5 mg (46%DRV)
		Selenium	51.1 ug (146%DRV)	Vit B6	0.6 mg (56%DRV)
		Iron	5.1 mg (47%DRV)	Vit B12	1.4 ug (54%DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://simplyfamilyrecipes.com/shrimp-recipes-for-kids/>

Octopus salad

6 servings

Prep time: 10 min

Cooking time: no cooking

Ingredients

- 400g pre-cooked octopus*
- 130g cucumber, chopped
- 300g cherry tomatoes
- Half a red onion
- 2 tbsp fresh parsley
- 3 green onions, sliced (white and green parts)
- 1 tsp dried oregano
- 2 tbsp lime juice
- 2 tbsp cider vinegar
- 3 tbsp olive oil
- Salt & pepper to taste

Steps (👨🍳⚠️: adult needed step)

1. Cut octopus, cucumber and cherry tomatoes into pieces. 👨🍳⚠️
2. Prepare dressing by combining olive oil, vinegar, lime juice, salt and pepper
3. Combine everything into a large bowl

Enjoy!

***Alternative:** Instead of octopus (which might not be easily available in your country), you can also use cooked calamaries

Fun facts: An octopus has three hearts! One actually stops when it swims, so octopus prefer crawling to keep energy. Octopus is rich in protein and low in fat, helping your muscles grow while giving your body important vitamins and minerals.

Nutrition (per serving)					
Energy	215 kcal (12%DRV*)	Fat	11.2 g (19% DRV)	Iodine	41.5 ug (46% DRV)
Carbs	6.7 g (3% DRV)	Saturated fats	1.8 g (9% DRV)	Zinc	2.5 mg (19% DRV)
Fiber	1.8 g (11% DRV)	Omega 3	0.2 g (83% DRV)	Vit A	48.8 ug (12% DRV)
Sugar	3.6 g (8% DRV)	Sodium	571 mg (34% DRV)	Vit D	0 ug (0% DRV)

Protein	20.9 g (75% DRV)	Calcium	99.9 mg (12% DRV)	Niacin	3.2 mg (27% DRV)
		Selenium	46.2 ug (132% DRV)	Vit B6	0.5 mg (51% DRV)
		Iron	7.2 mg (65% DRV)	Vit B12	24 ug (960% DRV)
* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)					
These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables					

Adapted from: https://www.simplyrecipes.com/recipes/ensalada_de_pulpo_octopus_salad/

Seaweed rice balls

Servings: 12 rice balls

Prep time: 15 min

Cooking time: 20 min

Ingredients

- 170g sushi (or short-medium) grain rice
- 4 seaweed sheets (nori)
- 2/3 tbsp low sodium soy sauce
- Half a teaspoon sesame oil
- Sesame seeds for garnish

Steps (👩🍳⚠️ : adult needed step)

1. Prepare the sticky rice (👩🍳⚠️) : Rinse the rice twice. Put it in a pot and add water until it's about 1 cm above the rice. Turn the heat to high. When it starts boiling, lower to medium, cover, and cook for 10 minutes. Then turn off the heat and let it rest for another 10 minutes with the lid on.
 2. Cut the seaweed: While the rice cooks, cut the seaweed sheets into very small pieces by hand.
 3. Mix the ingredients: When the rice has cooled a bit, put it in a large bowl. Add the shredded seaweed, soy sauce, and sesame oil.
 4. Shape the balls: Now the fun part! use your hands to mix everything together and shape the rice into small balls.
 5. Finish with sesame seeds: Place the balls on a plate and sprinkle sesame seeds on top.
- Now you have a delicious & health snack ! Enjoy

Fun facts: Seaweed absorb a lot of minerals from the water they grow in, making it a very nutrient rich food! They also grow very easily, which makes them both a very sustainable and healthy food to eat!

Nutrition (per serving – 3 rice balls)					
Energy	173 kcal (10% DRV*)	Fat	2 g (3% DRV)	Iodine	154 ug (171% DRV)
Carbs	33.6 g (15% DRV)	Saturated fats	0.3 g (2% DRV)	Zinc	0.9 mg (7% DRV)
Fiber	1.7 g (11% DRV)	Omega 3	0 g (2% DRV)	Vit A	48.7 ug (12% DRV)
Sugar	0 g (0% DRV)	Sodium	152.4 mg (9% DRV)	Vit D	0.9 mg (7% DRV)
Protein	4.2 g (15% DRV)	Calcium	15.6 mg (2% DRV)	Niacin	0.7 mg (6% DRV)
		Selenium	7.6 ug (22% DRV)	Vit B6	0.1 mg (6% DRV)
		Iron	1.4 mg (13% DRV)	Vit B12	0 ug (0% DRV)

* based on daily reference values for children between 7-10 (EFSA)
 These are estimates calculated based on generic product and average data available in European food composition tables

Adapted from: <https://jajabakes.com/seaweed-rice-balls/#recipe>